

Features of Students Ideas about Life Success

Olena STROYANOVSKA¹,
Liubov DOLYNSKA²,
Nataliia SHEVCHENKO³,
Svitlana YERMAKOVA⁴,
Liudmyla MATIASH-ZAIATS⁵,
Olena KRIUKOVA⁶

¹National Pedagogical Dragomanov University, Ukraine, cstroya@ua.fm

²National Pedagogical Dragomanov University, Ukraine, lbvdolinska@gmail.com

³Zaporizhzhia National University, Ukraine, shevchenkof.20@gmail.com

⁴Odessa State Academy of Civil Engineering and Architecture, Ukraine, ermakova.s2011@yandex.ua

⁵National Pedagogical Dragomanov University, Ukraine, ludmilamatyash@gmail.com

⁶National Pedagogical Dragomanov University, Ukraine, o.v.kryukova.knlu@gmail.com

Abstract: *The article presents the results of the analysis of scientific research studying the problem of life success and the features of the ideas about it among students of different genders and specialties. The features of understanding of success, successfulness, success in life, as well as the process of achieving it, which is determined by personal motivation for changes and development, accompanied by the energy status of activity, a positive emotional state, leading to the achievement of the desired goal in a certain area of social life and the well-being of the individual, have been determined. The results of the ascertaining experiment confirm the research assumption that the peculiarities of students' ideas about success in life are determined by their gender and the choice of professional specialization. It was found that girls and boys mainly focus on material values, their own self-realization and career growth, which can hinder the maximum comprehensive implementation and high quality of life of the individual in the future.*

Achieving goals and money as part of life's success are often high on the minds of students, regardless of their specialization. The exceptions are lawyers, for whom self-realization is more important, TV journalists, for whom money comes first, and actors, for whom the most important thing is to satisfy their needs and respect others.

Most students assess their level of life success as medium or low, which can reduce their level of motivation, self-esteem, self-efficacy in the implementation of aspirations and requires the development of special psychological recipes to optimize the process of achieving their life success.

Keywords: *success; successfulness; life success; the process of achieving life success; life satisfaction; motivation; self-efficacy; social status; self-realization; personal development.*

How to cite: Stroyanovska, O., Dolynska, L., Shevchenko, N., Yermakova, S., Matiash-Zaiats, L., & Kriukova, O. (2021). Features of Students Ideas about Life Success. *BRAIN. Broad Research in Artificial Intelligence and Neuroscience*, 12(1), 136-153. <https://doi.org/10.18662/brain/12.1/175>

Introduction

In the context of new political, social, economic realities of society, the desire of future specialists for success in life is a driving force that contributes to maximum professional implementation, efficiency, the formation of a new image of an employee who cares not only about his own material, but also psychological well-being, and an improvement in the quality of life.

The phenomenon of success has long attracted the attention of the social sciences, but many problems remain poorly understood, in particular, the characteristics and mechanisms of the formation of ideas about success, age, gender, professional differences in the understanding of success, factors in the formation of personal success, personal success, ways to optimize the achievement of life success at different age stages. Thus, the solution to the above problems remains promising and requires detailed study.

The psychological understanding of success is interpreted as the satisfaction of basic needs, a sense of growth, belief in one's own capabilities. It should be noted that modern scientific and psychological research studies the features of young people's ideas about success in life, the use of the situation of success in the process of education, the formation of an orientation towards achieving success in life in high school students, a situation of success as a means of forming achievement motivation in adolescents, the formation of vital competence of the personality of high school students, psychological characteristics of attribution of success in professional self-determination of students of higher educational institutions, psychological criteria of success in life of students of a pedagogical university, the influence of attitudes, belief in one's own strengths and the possibility of developing one's own abilities for success, features of certain forms of behavior, the presence of goals, a career plan, motivation, high self-efficacy, perseverance, affecting the success of the educational process and life in general, ways to increase student success with the help of special pedagogical methods of influence, Stroyanovska, (2020); L. Baletskaya, (2013); A. Galyuk, (2004); L. Maltz, (2011); Brewer, (1998); Deci, (1985); Dweck, (2007); Goto, (2009); King, Napa, (1998); Koekemoer, (2013); Levenson, Gottman, (1985); Raabe, (2007); Ryff (1995); Wilson, (2013); Palamarchuk, (2020); Nerubasska, (2020a); Nerubasska, (2020b); Melnyk, (2019); Sheremet, (2019); Gerasymova, (2019); Onishchuk, (2020); Maksymchuk, (2020a); Maksymchuk, (2020b).

The content of the concepts of success, successfulness, success in life and the process of achieving it

In connection with the social significance of the problem and the insufficiency of the corresponding systemic scientific developments, the *purpose of our study* was to study the state of the development of the problem of life success and the features of ideas about the life success of students of different specialties.

The content of the concept "success" is considered in psychology from different points of view and does not have an unambiguous understanding. For example, O. Mateyuk, (2012) suggests studying success through the level of material and social security, as well as life satisfaction; S. Klyuchnikov, (2002) adds to the aforementioned manifestations of success a sense of the harmony of one's life, a positive perception of the world, the absence of a feeling of unfulfillment, uselessness in life; I. Borovinskaya, (2017) focuses on the degree of satisfaction of the individual with the results achieved, O. Mishchenko, (2013) considers success as a real result in the form of a material standard of living, social status, Yu. Artamoshina, (2008) studies success as a special assessment by a person of the results of his own actions and efforts, as well as an indicator of his position in society, which determines the specifics of his social connections and relationships; V. Levchenko, (2014) emphasizes that real success is not only an opportunity to satisfy basic needs, but also personal growth and development; V. Vinkov, (2015) perceives it as the achievement of the desired goal in individual or group activity, corresponding to the requirements that are set by the nature of the activity itself and the subject's formed knowledge about the means of achieving the expected result; G. Mykhailyshyn, (2017) considers success, as a result, a value-based measure of the level of goal achievement, recognized by both an individual and society. Thus, we can conclude that success is considered in psychology as personal satisfaction with life, subjective and social approval of the achieved result of significant activity, personal growth and development.

Along with the concept of "success" in the psychological literature, the term "success" is often used. L. Dementiy, (2012) emphasizes the need to distinguish between these two concepts, understanding success as objective achievements in specific activities, and success as a subjective experience of success associated with the performance of their own activities, the productivity of their efforts. L. Maltz and A. Fedoseeva, (2011) add to this definition the possession of methods of activity that make it possible to move from single success to permanent. We do not agree with

this judgment and propose to consider success as a personal property, which is an important condition for achieving success, which means in this context a positive result of a certain purposeful activity. Confirmation of our opinion can be found in the works of other researchers. In particular, G. Mykhailyshyn, (2017) defines success as a certain way of life of an individual, which is aimed at achieving success through purposeful activity and the desire to develop harmoniously in all spheres of social life. I. Borovinskaya, (2017) believes that success is the result of a person's activity, which makes sense for himself and is recognized by others, and success is a state of experiencing personal success. Researcher O. Mateyuk, (2012) notes that success covers not one random phenomenon, but repeatedly verified life experience, which is formed thanks to positive thinking, lifestyle and motivation to achieve this goal with the help of purposeful activity, the desire to constantly develop. I. Vernudina, (2010) speaks of success as a process of self-development and self-realization in one's own living space, the desire to achieve Acme. I. Korduban and L. Lazarenko, (2007) study success as a dynamic socio-psychological characteristic of an individual, which presupposes the presence of socially recognized achievements, focus on success, satisfaction with the process and the result of one's own life. Thus, the above situations prove the difference between success and successfulness.

In many psychological works, the concepts of success and success in life are identified and are not considered as different phenomena. In our opinion, success is a broader concept than success in life. I. Borovynska, (2017) notes that success in life is more subjective in comparison with success, since it is associated with the life project, plans and tasks of an individual. In addition, she draws attention to the fact that only a mature person can build his life project and choose a strategy for its implementation, based on his own experience and individual needs. Competence and self-efficacy are essential components of this process. Yu. Ilyina, (2008) examines life success through the prism of building and functioning of a mental model, which ensures the achievement of success and includes the following components: financial, communicative, experienced, family, age, health component, gender, motivational-value, emotional, professional. Other scientists, Yu. Artamoshina, (2008), I. Feldman, (2014) highlight such aspects of life success as having satisfactory living conditions, employment, relationships with a partner, indicators on the scale of anxiety and depression, happy family and health. Thus, to study the specifics and content of the success of a particular person and his life path as a whole, it is more expedient to use the term "life success".

A detailed study of the problem of success allowed us to define a more systemic, in comparison with others, understanding of the process of achieving life success. By the process of achieving success in life, we mean stable and long-term activity, which is determined by personal motivation for change and development, is accompanied by a certain energetic state of activity, a positive emotional state and contributes to the achievement of the desired goal in a certain area of the life of society and the well-being of the individual in its various aspects.

So, we have defined and theoretically studied such concepts as success, life success, successfulness and the process of achieving life success. We would like not to equate the last two concepts, because, in our opinion, success is a personal quality that consists of many personal formations that contribute to the constant experience of success in various spheres of life, and the process of achieving success in life is an activity that is characterized by the presence difficult obstacles, the loss of activity guidelines, a change in value orientations, the search for new ways to solve life's contradictions, but at the same time a constant desire for success, which subsequently leads to it. Thus, successfulness can indirectly influence the process of achieving success in life, which means that the first concept is broader than the second.

Following the foregoing, we came to the conclusion that personal motivation for change and development is the driving force behind achieving success in life, which is based on personal ideas about life success, which are formed under the influence of society and the experience of the individual's own life. Domestic and foreign researchers studied the personality features of ideas about life success and found that such ideas depend on age, gender and professional activity. For example, K. Melashchenko, (2009) investigated the gender-role features of ideas about life success and determined that for women this phenomenon implies compliance with social expectations regarding the purpose of women, such as having children and caring for a family, and for men, achievements are more significant. in the social sphere (career, prestige, high status, etc.). Yu. Artamoshina, (2008) found similar gender-role differences: in men, success is predominantly associated with the presence of social connections, material security, power and participation in political activity, in women - with health, good education and family. A. Galyuk, (2004) pays attention to the fact that in the ideas of the older generation, achieving success is associated with the ability to comply with norms, but in the ideas of young people, the ability to find non-standard opportunities and luck play an important role. Scientists

have in common the belief that a high material status and professionalism are indicators of success.

As you know, any mental phenomenon has a neuropsychological nature and is conditioned, and also accompanied by the peculiarities of the central nervous system, the activity of the cortical regions of the brain, changes in autonomic functions. Based on the content of the concept of success in life, it should be noted the process of its achievement, which is ensured by the joint integrative work of various brain zones, each of which makes its own specific contribution to the implementation of a certain link in the functional system.

A special place in this process belongs to the frontal parts of the brain, which is a complex formation that provides self-regulation of mental activity in such its components as goal-setting in connection with motives and intentions, the choice of means of achieving the goal, monitoring the implementation of the achievement program and its correction, comparison of the obtained result of activity with the original problem, Amen, (2018); Sitnikova, Rosen, Lord, & West, (2014). It is the prefrontal regions and their interaction with the hippocampus, as shown by clinical and psychological data, Matsumoto & Tanaka, 2004; Numan, (2015) are directly related to the integrative organization of movements and actions throughout the entire length of their implementation and, above all, at the level of arbitrary regulation.

Also, the presence of stress has a special effect on the success of the activity. A small amount of it can even contribute to success, while an excessive amount, on the contrary, leads to an increase in cortisol levels and a decrease in serotonin and dopamine levels, and therefore a decrease in energy and slowdown in body and speech movements, Ashby, Isen & Turken, (1999); Trainor, (2011; Volkow, Wang, Newcorn, Kollins, Wiga, Telang, Swanson, (2011).

Thus, success is of a neuropsychological nature, due to the interaction of the frontal regions of the brain, the hippocampus and the mesolimbic system.

The empirical studies we have studied, in our opinion, do not sufficiently generalize modern social trends in the development of people's ideas about life success. A more detailed study of them in the younger generation will allow not only to determine the gender-role and professional characteristics of life guidelines for achieving success, but also to develop psycho correctional means in order to optimize them in the most favorable period of a person's growing up, in particular, studying at a higher educational institution. Thus, we *put forward a hypothesis* that the features of

the ideas about the life success of students of different specialties are determined by their gender and the choice of professional specialization.

Features of students' ideas about success in life and assessment of its level

In order to study the level and features of the young generation's ideas about success in life, using the author's questionnaire, we studied 250 third-year students of the Kiev National University of Culture and Art aged 20 to 22 years of various specialties (89.6% - female subjects, 10.4 % - male subjects).

According to the recommendations of D. Cohen (1988), in our work we used the value of the probability of error of the first kind (1-alpha), which is traditional in psychological, social and behavioral studies, which is equal to 0.05. The study included 250 people, which with $p = 0.05$ and the expected average statistical effect allows achieving the power of statistical methods (beta) greater than 0.99. To achieve a power level that can be considered high (beta = 0.9) at $p = 0.05$, and the expected average level of effect, 191 people are sufficient in the study. The number of subjects exceeded the recommended sample size, which significantly improved the quality of our study.

The results of the empirical study are shown below in Figures 1-3. As can be seen in Figure 1, for female subjects (89.6%), the main components of success in life are achieving goals (20%), money (16.8%), self-realization (16%), respect for loved ones and other people (11, 2%), good job (8.2%). Among other components, female students often mention career (7.2%), recognition and glory (6.8%), satisfaction (5.6%), happy family (1.6%). It should be noted that a small percentage of girls (0.8%) are focused on the importance of such components of life success as health, dream, happiness, independence, talent, love, stability, etc.

Figure: 1 Female students' ideas about the main components of life success (%)

Based on the analysis of the results, it can be concluded that female students focus their attention on material values, their own self-realization and career growth.. Love, family, children, health remain in the last places in their ideas about success in life, which, in our opinion, is associated with their desire to realize themselves as much as possible in their future profession to improve the quality of their life, the social orientation of the young generation towards material values. As can be seen in Figure 2, for male subjects (10.4%), the main components of success in life are achievement of goals, recognition and glory (4%), self-realization (2.4%), money and self-satisfaction (1.6%).

Among other components of the ideas about success in life, students often mention (0.8%) career, respect for loved ones and other people, good job, independence, professionalism. It should be noted that young men also focus on material values, self-realization and career, and family, love and children are not mentioned by them at all, which, in our opinion, refers to the stereotypes of society about the importance, first of all, of the material condition of a man and the presence prestigious work to assess its success.

Figure: 2 *Students' ideas about the main components of life success (%)*

Summarizing the results, we can say that a significant number of students represent success as achieving their own goals (24%), having money and self-realization (18.4%), respect for loved ones and other people (12%), recognition and glory (10, 8%), good job (9%) and career (8%), which proves the importance of material achievements for them. This fact contradicts the results of previous studies by other authors, who pointed to a greater orientation of girls' ideas about success in life towards having children and caring for a family. This state of affairs, in our opinion, may be associated with the development of gender equality, namely, when women can maximize their opportunities at work, sometimes even exceeding the professional activities of men in their efforts and results. In connection with the emergence of such opportunities, many women stop treating family and childbirth as components of success in life, which, in our opinion, is a prerequisite for reducing the number of marriages and childbirth in the country.

If we analyze the influence of the professional orientation of students on their ideas about life success, then we can say that the achievement of goals as a component of life success often takes the first place in the ideas of students, despite their specialization. The exceptions are lawyers, for whom self-realization is the most important, TV journalists, who have money in the first place, and actors, for whom the most important are self-satisfaction and respect for others. For most students of various specialties, money is also of paramount importance in assessing life success (only translators, economists and filmmakers do not focus on them - recognition, fame, self-realization and good work are more important for

them). Students of several specialties (sociologists, lawyers and filmmakers) focus on a happy family, which, in our opinion, is due to the fact that specialists in these professions often consider issues of family well-being, realizing its importance for the comprehensive development of the individual. It should be noted that it is for creative professions (directors, photographers, actors) that the experience of recognition and glory is important, which is explained by the public nature of their activities. It is interesting that for translators, lawyers and economists, an important part of life's success is respect for loved ones and other people, which, in our opinion, is associated with the prestige of the above professions and the expectation of public approval for the correct choice of socially significant professions. Only actors, in their ideas about success in life, recall self-satisfaction, which indicates their desire to realize their creative talent, enjoying self-actualization.

Thus, based on the results of empirical research, we can conclude that gender and choice of professional specialization significantly affect the content of students' ideas about life success, which proves our hypothesis.

In the course of the empirical research, the level of assessment of their own success by students of different genders and professional specialization was also studied (Fig. 3).

Figure: 3 *Students' assessment of the level of success in life (%)*

To check the equality of the mean values of the two groups (male and female), we used the Student's t-test for independent samples, which indicates a statistical similarity in the distribution of success rates among girls and boys ($t < p$, $t = 0.49$), which means, independence of the level of assessment of life success from gender. As can be seen in Figure 3, young men are nevertheless more prone to a high assessment of their own success

than women, which may indicate their ability to quickly realize their ideas of success due to the presence of more opportunities to achieve their own goals, gain recognition and glory, self-realization and earning money while still studying. Girls have a wider range of ideas about success in life, including love, family, children, which takes more time and effort than success in work and their own development.

It is interesting that the majority of students, both girls and boys, rate their level of success in life as medium (54.6% and 53.3%) or low (20.1% and 13.4%). This situation, in our opinion, is most likely due to the fact that students perceive success in life as a phenomenon that must be achieved with difficult efforts for a long time, and associate it (as noted above) with achieving their own goals, having money, good work and careers. An underestimation of one's own success at the moment can negatively affect the self-esteem of students in general, making it difficult to overcome obstacles and maintain the necessary level of motivation for development in the future.

Conclusions

The process of achieving success in life is a stable and long-term activity, conditioned by personal motivation for change and development, accompanied by a certain energetic state of activity, a positive emotional state and leading to the achievement of the desired goal in a certain sphere of the life of society and the well-being of the individual in its various aspects.

The basis of motivation for change and development is personal ideas about the success of life, the analysis of which is necessary to optimize the process of achieving life success in the most favorable period of a person's growing up, in particular, studying at a higher educational institution. Comparative analysis of the research results of other authors and the results obtained in this study confirms the hypothesis that gender and choice of professional specialization significantly affect the content of students' ideas about life success. An interesting fact is that both girls and boys have a shift in the orientation of their ideas about success towards material satisfaction, which contradicts the results of previous studies, in which the features of women's ideas about life success were based on social expectations about the purpose of women (social contacts, family, birth of children). So, for girls, the main components of success in life are achieving goals, money, self-realization, respect for loved ones and other people, good job. Love, family, children, health are often mentioned, but they remain in

the last places in their perception of the success of life, which, in our opinion, is connected with the desire of female students to realize themselves as much as possible in their future profession to improve the quality of their life, the social orientation of the young generation towards material values. For young men, the main components of success in life are achieving goals, recognition and glory, self-realization, money and self-satisfaction. Thus, males also focus mainly on material values, self-realization and career, and family, love and children are not mentioned by them at all, which is associated with stereotypes of society about the importance, first of all, of the material condition of a man and the availability of a prestigious job for evaluating its success.

It should be noted that the change in the emphasis of women's ideas about success in life from caring for a family and having children to professional, career and material growth is associated, in our opinion, with the development of gender equality in society, expanding opportunities for women to realize themselves as much as possible in work, which can lead to a decrease in the number of marriages and childbirth in the country. The material orientation of the ideas of young people of different sexes about the success of life can lead to a desire only for material wealth and career growth, one-sided personality development, a lack of understanding of the need for deep interpersonal relationships, the loss of important guidelines for the timely construction of family relationships, the birth and upbringing of children, which means thereby hinder the maximum, versatile self-realization and high quality of life of the individual in the future.

Students' professional orientation also influences on their ideas of success in life. Achieving goals as part of life success is often ranked first in the views of students regardless of their specialization. For most students of various specialties, money is also of paramount importance in assessing success in life. Students of several specialties (sociologists, lawyers and filmmakers) reproduce a happy family in their ideas about success in life. For creative professions (directors, photographers, actors), recognition and glory are important in experiencing life success. For translators, lawyers and economists respect for loved ones and other people is an important component of success in life. Only actors remember self-satisfaction in their ideas of success in life.

Most young people assess their level of success in life as medium or low, focusing their attention on the stereotype that success must be achieved through complex efforts over a long time, and forgetting about the importance of today's achievements for the future, which can reduce their level of motivation, self-esteem and self-efficacy.

The prospect of further research on the problem of success in life is a comprehensive study of the reasons for the material orientation of the young generation's ideas about success in life and the development of special psychological measures to optimize the process of achieving it.

References

- Amen, D. A. (2018). Neuroscience reveals the secrets to success. Retrieved from <https://www.thedailybeast.com/the-neuroscience-of-success?ref=scroll>
- Artamoshina Yu., (2008) *Osobennosti predstavleniy ob uspekhe zhenshchin, vpolnyayushchikh traditsionnyye i netraditsionnyye professional'nyye roli* [Features of ideas about the success of women performing traditional and nontraditional professional roles]: dissertation for the degree of Candidate of Psychological Sciences. M.: Moscow Psychological-Sociological Institute. <https://www.dissercat.com/content/osobennosti-predstavlenii-ob-uspekhe-zhenshchin-vpolnyayushchikh-traditsionnyye-i-netraditsi>
- Ashby, F. G., Isen, A. M., & Turken, A. U. (1999). A neuropsychological theory of positive affect and its influence on cognition. *Psychological Review*, 106(3), 529–550. doi:<http://dx.doi.org.ezproxy.loras.edu/10.1037/0033-295X.106.3.529>
- Baletskaya L., (2013) *Atributy professional'nogo uspekha. Sovremennyye problemy nauki i obrazovaniya* [Attributes of professional success. Modern problems of science and education]: 4.
- Borovynska I., (2017) *Do psykholohichnogo rozuminnya ponyat' "uspikb", "uspishnist", "zhyttyevyy uspihb", "zhyttyeva uspishnist"* [To the psychological understanding of the concepts "success", "successfulness", "life success", "life successfulness"] *Scientific Bulletin of Kherson State University. Series: Psychological Sciences*: 3 (2), 142–148.
- Brewer, M. B. (1998). Who is this “we”?: levels of collective identity and self-representations. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 71(1), 83-93. doi: 10.1037/0022-3514.71.1.83
- Cohen, J. (1988). *Statistical power analysis for the behavioral sciences* (2nd ed.). Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum. <http://www.utstat.toronto.edu/~brunner/oldclass/378f16/readings/CohenPower.pdf>.
- Deci, E. (1985). The general causality orientations scale: self-determination in personality. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 19, 109–134. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/0092656685900236>.
- Dementiy L., (2012) *Otvettvennost' kak determinanta sotsial'nykh predstavleniy ob uspekhe i usloviyakh yego dostizheniya* [Responsibility as a determinant of social ideas

- about success and the conditions for achieving it]. Bulletin of Omsk University: 3, 289–295. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/otvetstvennost-kak-determinanta-sotsialnyh-predstavleniy-ob-uspehe-i-usloviyah-ego-dostizheniya/viewer>
- Diener, E., Emmons, R. A., Larsen, R. J. & Griffin, Sh. (1985). The satisfaction with life scale. *Journal of Personality Assessment*, 49(1), 71–75. doi: 10.1207/s15327752jpa4901_13
- Dweck, S. (2007). *Mindset: The New Psychology of Success Paperback*. <https://www.amazon.com/Mindset-Psychology-Carol-S-Dweck/dp/0345472322>.
- Feldman I., (2014) *Polovozrastnyye osobennosti zhibiznennogo uspekha u menedzherov* [Age and sex characteristics of life success among managers]. Bulletin Tula State University. Series "Humanities". Tula: Publishing house of Tula State University: 3, 73–84.
<http://dspace.nbu.gov.ua/bitstream/handle/123456789/28831/18-Melashchenko.pdf?sequence=1>
- Galyuk A., (2004) *Osobennosti predstavleniy molodezhi o zhibiznennom uspeke v sovremennoy Rossii* [Features of young people's ideas about success in life in modern Russia]: dissertation for the degree of Candidate of Sociological Sciences. Ekaterinburg. <https://elar.urfu.ru/bitstream/10995/343/2/urgu0272s.pdf>
- Gerasymova, I., Maksymchuk, B., Bilozero, M., Chernetska, Yu., Matviichuk, T., Solovyov, V., & Maksymchuk, I. (2019). Forming professional mobility in future agricultural specialists: the sociohistorical context. *Revista Romaneasca pentru Educatie Multidimensionala*, 11 (4), 345-361.
<http://lumenpublishing.com/journals/index.php/rrem/article/view/1604/pdf>
- Goto, T. (2009). Psychology of Success: Overcoming Barriers to Pursuing Further Education. *The Journal of Continuing Higher Education* 57: 10–21.
<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/07377360902810744?scroll=top&needAccess=true>. http://science.ncstu.ru/articles/hs/2007_05/psychology/09.pdf.
http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/nvkhp_2017_3%282%29_26
<https://www.science-education.ru/ru/article/view?id=9865>
- Ilyina Yu., (2008) *Psykholohiya uspikhu: ontolohiya problematyky. Aktual'ni problemy psykholohiyi* [Psychology of success: an ontology of problems]. *Current problems of psychology*, 8, 45–56.
<http://www.newlearning.org.ua/sites/default/files/praci/zbirnyk-2008/6.htm>
- King, L., & Napa, Ch. K. (1998). What makes a life good? *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 75, 156-165. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.75.1.156>.

- Klyuchnikov S., (2002) *Faktor uspekha: Novaya psikhologiya samorazvitiya* [Success factor: New psychology of self-development]. M.: Belovodye. <https://klex.ru/35z>
- Koekemoer, E. (2013). Exploring the Attainment of Career Success. *Journal of Psychology in Africa*, 23, 601–608. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/14330237.2013.10820673>
- Korduban I., Lazarenko L., (2007) *Psikhologicheskaya kharakteristika fenomenov uspekha i uspeshnost'* [Psychological characteristics of the phenomena of success and successfulness]. *Collection of scientific papers of the North Caucasus Federal University. Series "Humanities"*, 5, 94–119.
- Levchenko V., (2014) *Sekrety uspekha i uspeshnosti sovremennogo cheloveka* [Secrets of success and successfulness of a modern person]: [monograph]. M.: FLINTA. <https://docplayer.ru/36559388-Sekrety-uspeha-i-uspeshnosti-sovremennogo-cheloveka.html>
- Levenson, R., & Gottman, J. (1985). Physiological and affective predictors of change in relationship satisfaction. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 49, 85-94. <https://bpl.berkeley.edu/docs/28-Physiological%20and%20affective%20predictors85.pdf>.
- Lyubomirsky, S. (2008). *The how of happiness: A scientific approach to getting the life you want*. New York: Penguin Press. <https://www.amazon.com/How-Happiness-Approach-Getting-Life/dp/0143114956>.
- Maksymchuk, B., Gurevych, R., Matviichuk, T., Surovov, O., Stepanchenko, N., Opushko, N., Sitovskiy, A., Kosynskiy, E., Bogdanyuk, A., Vakoliuk, A., Solovyov, V., & Maksymchuk, I. (2020). Training Future Teachers to Organize School Sport. *Revista Romaneasca Pentru Educatie Multidimensionala*, 12(4), 310-327. <https://doi.org/10.18662/rrem/12.4/347>
- Maksymchuk, B., Matviichuk, T., Solovyov, V., Davydenko, H., Soichuk, R., Khurtenko, O., Groshovenko, O., Stepanchenko, N., Andriychuk, Y., Grygorenko, T., Duka, T., Pidlypniak, I., Gurevych, R., Kuzmenko, V., & Maksymchuk, I. (2020). Developing Healthcare Competency in Future Teachers. *Revista Romaneasca Pentru Educatie Multidimensionala*, 12(3), 24-43. <https://doi.org/10.18662/rrem/12.3/307>
- Malts L., Fedoseeva A., (2011) *Psikhologicheskiye kriterii zhiznennoy uspeshnosti studentov pedagogicheskogo VUZa* [Psychological criteria of life success of students of a pedagogical university].M. http://psysis.ru/?PSIHOLOGICHESKIE_KRITERII_ZhIZNENNOI_USPESHNOSTI_STUDENTOV...
- Mateyuk O., (2012) *Uspishnist' osobystosti: sutnist' ta zmist fenomena* [Success of personality: essence and content of the phenomenon] Bulletin of the

- National Academy of the State Border Guard Service of Ukraine:4.
http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/Vnadps_2012_4_31.
- Matsumoto, K., & Tanaka, K. (2004). The role of the medial prefrontal cortex in achieving goals. *Current Opinion in Neurobiology*, 14(2), 178–185.
doi:<http://dx.doi.org.ezproxy.loras.edu/10.1016/j.conb.2004.03.005>
- Melashchenko K., (2009) *Zhyttyevyy uspih u hendernomu vymiri: sotsiologichni rozvidky. Sotsial'ni vymiry suspil'stva* [Life success in the gender dimension: sociological intelligence. Social dimensions of society]: Collection of scientific works K.: Institute of Horticulture of the National Academy of Agrarian Sciences of Ukraine, 1(12), 208–219.
- Melyk, N., Bidyuk, N., Kalenskyi, A., Maksymchuk. B., Bakhmat, N., Matviienko, O. ... Maksymchuk, I. (2019). Models and organizational characteristics of preschool teachers' professional training in some EU countries and Ukraine. *Zbornik Instituta za pedagogika istrazivanja*, 51(1), 46–93.
<https://ipisr.org.rs/images/pdf/zbornik-51/Natalija-Meljnik.pdf>
- Mishchenko O., (2013) *Psyholobichni osoblyvosti uyavlen' osoblyvosti pro ekonomichno uspihnu lyudynu* [Psychological features of personal ideas about an economically successful person]. *Current issues of psychology 11: Issue 8, Part 2*, 85–95. <https://res.in.ua/mishchenko-o-o-psiholobichni-osoblyvosti-uyavlene-osoblyvosti-pr.html>
- Mykhailyshyn H., (2017) *Uspishnist' osoblyvosti: filosofskiy ta psyholobichno-pedahohichnyy kontekst* [Personality success: philosophical and psychological-pedagogical context]. *Scientific thinking*, 2, 50–56.
<http://naukam.triada.in.ua/images/files/zbornik9.pdf>
- Nerubasska, A., Maksymchuk, B. (2020). The Demarkation of Creativity, Talent and Genius in Humans: a Systemic Aspect. *Postmodern Openings*, 11 (2), 240-255.
<https://www.lumenpublishing.com/journals/index.php/po/article/view/2625>
- Nerubasska, A., Palshkov, K., & Maksymchuk, B. (2020). A Systemic Philosophical Analysis of the Contemporary Society and the Human: New Potential. *Postmodern Openings*, 11(4), 275-292.
<https://doi.org/10.18662/po/11.4/235>
- Numan, R. (2015). A Prefrontal-Hippocampal Comparator for Goal-Directed Behavior: The Intentional Self and Episodic Memory. *Frontiers in behavioral neuroscience*, 9, 323. doi:10.3389/fnbeh.2015.00323
- Onishchuk, I., Ikonnikova, M., Antonenko, T., Kharchenko, I., Shestakova, S., Kuzmenko, N., & Maksymchuk, B. (2020). Characteristics of Foreign Language Education in Foreign Countries and Ways of Applying Foreign Experience in Pedagogical Universities of Ukraine. *Revista Romaneasca Pentru*

- Educatie Multidimensionala*, 12(3), 44-65.
<https://doi.org/10.18662/rrem/12.3/308>
- Palamarchuk, O., Gurevych, R., Maksymchuk, B., Gerasymova, I., Fushtey, O., Logutina, N., Kalashnik, N., Kylyvnyk, A., Haba, I., Matviichuk, T., Solovyov, V., & Maksymchuk, I. (2020). Studying Innovation as the Factor in Professional Self-Development of Specialists in Physical Education and Sport. *Revista Romaneasca Pentru Educatie Multidimensionala*, 12(4), 118-136.
<https://doi.org/10.18662/rrem/12.4/337>
- Raabe, B. (2007). Action regulation theory and career self-management. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 70 (2): 297–311. <http://psycnet.apa.org/record/2007-04240-006>.
- Ryff, C. C. (1995). The structure of psychological well-being revisited. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 69(4), 719–727.
<http://www.midus.wisc.edu/findings/pdfs/830.pdf>.
- Schachter, S., & Singer, J. (1962). Cognitive, social, and physiological determinants of emotional state. *Psychological Review*, 69(5), 379–399.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/14497895/>.
- Sheremet M., Leniv Z., Loboda V., Maksymchuk B. (2019) The development level of smart information criterion for specialists' readiness for inclusion implementation in education. *Information Technologies and Learning Tools*, 72, 273-285. <https://journal.iitta.gov.ua/index.php/itlt/article/view/2561>
- Sitnikova, T., Rosen, B. R., Lord, L. D., & West, W. C. (2014). Understanding human original actions directed at real-world goals: the role of the lateral prefrontal cortex. *NeuroImage*, 103, 91–105.
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4312188/>
- Stroianovska, O., Dolynska, L., Shevchenko, N., Andriiashyna, N., Melnyk, I., & Tsybuliak, N. (2020). The Influence of the Professional Orientation of Students of Different Gender on Their Ideas of Happiness. *BRAIN. Broad Research in Artificial Intelligence and Neuroscience*, 11(3), 51-71.
<https://doi.org/10.18662/brain/11.4/141>
- Trainor, B. (2011). Stress responses and the mesolimbic dopamine system: social contexts and sex differences. *Hormones and behavior*, 60(5), 457–69.
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3217312/>
- Vernudina I., (2010) *Psyhobolohichni chynnyky uspikhu: sproba komparatyvnoho analizu* [Psychological factors of success: an attempt at comparative analysis]. *Education and management: 2/3*, 86–91.
<http://lib.vippo.org.ua/periodyka.php?book=386>
- Vinkov V., (2015) *Uyanlennya pro zhyttyevyy uspikh: stan rozroblenosti problemyky v sotsial'niy psyhobolohiyi* [The idea of life success: the state of development of issues in social psychology]. *Problems of political psychology*, 2, 221–231.
http://psy-lpr.at.ua/Materials/zb2_16_.pdf

- Volkow, N. D., Wang, G. J., Newcorn, J. H., Kollins, S. H., Wiga, T. L., Telang, F., . . . Swanson, J. M. (2011). Motivation deficit in ADHD is associated with dysfunction of the dopamine reward pathway. *Molecular Psychiatry*, *16*(11), 1147–1154. <http://dx.doi.org.ezproxy.loras.edu/10.1038/mp.2010.97>
- Wilson, T. (2013). *The Psychology of Success: Helping Students Achieve*. LiveScience. <https://www.livescience.com/38164-psychological-interventions-for-kids.html>.